

Towards 5G/6G Data Harmonization through NLP and Semantic Web Technologies

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Abstract—Telecommunication systems utilize several mechanisms to collect data from 5G/6G-enabled IoT. In the 5G/6G community, various AI techniques and tools are applied to 5G/6G data to monitor, predict, and make decisions. Therefore, 5G/6G data must be interoperable for monitoring, prediction, and decision support systems. However, 5G/6G data are typically mapped in local data models for local applications, which poses challenges to using them in different or cross-domain applications due to a lack of interoperability issues. In this paper, we propose an approach to support and enhance the interoperability of 5G/6G data through NLP and Semantic Web technologies to achieve 5G/6G data harmonization.

Index Terms—5G/6G data, QoE, interoperability, data harmonization, knowledge graph.

I. INTRODUCTION

Data collected in 5G/6G application scenarios often serve a particular application-specific purpose, which leads to heterogeneous data models if these applications don't use domain-specific ontologies or standards. Hence, diverse 5G/6G data models must be aligned with the end application to make them interoperable before other applications use them. This poses a significant challenge to interoperability when integrating 5G/6G data into a pre-established system. Interoperability of 5G/6G data can only be successful by aligning the syntactic (structure) and semantic (meaning) interoperability of the data/information they share. In this line, the alignment tasks are cumbersome and challenging for an application engineer during the integration of 5G/6G applications since it requires a manual review of the relevant data models of applications and domain-specific ontologies or standards that he could potentially align with the 5G/6G data. Additionally, before aligning each term used in the 5G/6G data with the concepts (terms) defined in the domain-specific ontologies or standards, all related terms in the given ontologies must be considered according to their similarity or relatedness.

This paper discusses Quality of Experience (QoE) in 5G/6G applications from different angles. Initially, we provide relevant definitions of objective and subjective metrics to measure the QoE in 5G/6G-enabled applications. Next, we motivate the data interoperability problem in the context of QoE data alignment and provide an approach to address

this problem along with preliminary results. Finally, as part of the case study, we utilize Machine Learning (ML) algorithms to develop a QoE prediction model. Our work showcases the potential of using semantic technologies and machine learning techniques in the context of QoE prediction.

II. QOE LITERATURE REVIEW

QoE provides quantified subjective and objective methodologies for depicting the users' satisfaction with a specific service or application. QoE prediction estimates subjective QoE scores based on various network measurements and service specifications. In this context, ML and Deep Learning (DL) have been investigated to predict QoE levels in communication networks for multiple applications. [1] considers ML-based prediction of users' QoE in Software-defined Networking (SDN). First, a subjective evaluation based on Degradation Category Ratings (DCR) is conducted. The collected data is then used to train and assess the performance of four ML solutions: Decision Tree (DT), neural network, K-nearest Neighbours (KNN), and Random Forest (RF). In this work, both full reference parameters and application metrics have been utilized for QoE prediction. In [4], a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) has been utilized for continuous QoE prediction in video streaming applications. This work shows CNNs can provide accurate QoE estimates while maintaining low computational complexity. To improve QoE in edge-enabled Internet of Things (IoT) networks, the authors in [8] developed an improved QoE model and proposed a novel Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) solution. The adopted QoE model uses Quality of Service (QoS) information derived from the computation offloading processes.

QoE aims to quantify human satisfaction and perception of a service. However, depending on their application, people's experience services can be subject to varying parameters. Thus, researchers studying QoE have pointed out the importance of considering the unique nature and demands of different sets of applications. For instance, the IoT connects many devices to the Internet. These devices are developed to perform different tasks and can be used in various applications. IoT devices are typically designed to operate with little

TABLE I
QoE PREDICTION ERROR OVER THE TWO DATASETS

MODEL	LIVE_NFLX		Aleksandrlvchenko	
	MAE	MSE	MAE	MSE
LR	0.1142	0.0214	0.1138	0.0211
KRR	0.1115	0.0213	0.1240	0.0243
SVR	0.1213	0.0239	0.1099	0.0186

to no human involvement, which creates a challenge when assessing the application QoE. Because of this, researchers started investigating QoE aspects in emerging 5G/6G-enabled IoT applications. The authors in [11] conducted an experimental study of QoE parameters for smart-wearable devices. They included 40 human subjects in a free-living environment with five different wearable devices and used the results for QoE modelling. [15] provided a QoE measurement framework for IoT applications and tested their methodology in Jakarta Smart City. This work targeted six public services, including garbage trucks, fire and rescue services, and city bus transportation.

III. A CASE STUDY: QoE PREDICTION ACROSS DATASETS

QoE prediction models are particularly utilized to help improve content delivery services by making resource allocation decisions to enhance the user experience. Multiple features can be exploited in video delivery services to predict user satisfaction with the videos. This includes information about the video content, network parameters, and display specifications. Combining QoE data from different sources can be beneficial in various contexts, one of which is QoE prediction. However, different video services may adopt different terminologies in their QoE frameworks. This section tests the feasibility of applying QoE prediction across two different QoE datasets. We use the *LIVE_NFLX* dataset [2] for fitting QoE models and apply the models for predicting the subjective QoE scores in Aleksandrlvchenko’s QoE-Assessment dataset [12]. We use two features to predict the final Mean Opinion Score (MOS). Namely, the mean Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and the number of stalling events. We selected these two metrics as they strongly relate to the users’ perception of video content. Intuitively, higher PSNR values and fewer stalling events should improve QoE. The two datasets use different labels to refer to these features. To harmonize the data from the two datasets, we manually map the terms from both datasets that correspond to these features. We also match and normalize the subjective scores from each dataset according to their scoring ranges to work with unified data scales.

We utilize three regression methods in our experiments: Linear Regression (LR), Kernel Ridge Regression (KRR), and Support Vector Regression (SVR). We first fit each of the three models using the *LIVE_NFLX* dataset and assess their performance over a test portion of the same dataset. We then utilize the same models, fitted using only the *LIVE_NFLX* dataset, to predict the QoE scores derived from Aleksandrlvchenko’s dataset. Figure 1 illustrates the original (true) data points and the fitted prediction models. Normalized MOS are shown for both datasets, obtained from pairs of stalling events and PSNR values. In Figure 1, the

MOS scores are shown for the test part of the *LIVE_NFLX* dataset, along with the predictions from each model. The unseen data points of Aleksandrlvchenko’s dataset are depicted in Figure 1, along with the MOS values from the trained models. The resulting mean absolute error Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and the Mean Squared Error (MSE) values are summarized in Table I. The results show that QoE prediction models can be utilized across different datasets. All three models provided decent predictions when applied to the unseen dataset. This held even though Aleksandrlvchenko’s dataset contains data points with larger input ranges for both PSNR and stalling events. This highlights the ability of the QoE models to extrapolate for larger input ranges.

IV. QoE DATA HARMONIZATION

5G/6G refers to the next generation of wireless communication technology. One of the hot research areas for 6G technology is in conjunction with edge Artificial Intelligence (AI), which involves processing data at or near the source rather than transmitting it back to a centralized data centre for analysis. This could significantly improve areas such as autonomous vehicles, healthcare, and manufacturing. However, this requires harmonizing 5G/6G data in different applications with different data formats or labels to record measurement data. In the data integration process, the following two harmonization scenarios arise:

- 1) Data model to data model: When two different applications with different data models want to use each other’s data, their data models must be harmonized to use their datasets as a single source. The case study presented in the previous section is based on this scenario.
- 2) Data model to standard/ontology: An application’s data model must adapt domain-specific standards and ontologies so that all other domain-specific applications can use its datasets as a single source. This scenario enhances the interoperability of a data model.

In both scenarios, we must overcome syntactic (different data representation formats) and semantic (using different terms in data models to label the same data) interoperability issues of the 5G/6G data. Therefore, someone must manually inspect the given datasets, standards, or ontologies before they can be harmonized as a single data source. Harmonizing data can become a cumbersome task when done manually. However, Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Semantic Web (SW) technologies can support the data harmonization process.

A. Approach

In [13], Singh et al. introduce a Data and Information Interoperability Model (DIIM) to enable and enhance the interoperability of the IoT data for Smart Water Network (SWN) applications. To achieve syntactic interoperability in Figure 2, given data is converted into Resource Description Framework (RDF) format by using a RDF-converter [16], then it can be transformed into an application-specific format. To achieve semantic interoperability between two applications, similar terms used in the data models of given applications are linked via annotations in the RDF graphs, representing the data of these applications. To address the semantic issue, we follow the DIIM approach that takes

Fig. 1. QoE prediction results obtained from three different prediction models. (a) predicted MOS scores over the *LIVE_NFLX* dataset. (b) predicted MOS scores over *AleksandrIvchenko* dataset

Fig. 2. Data and Information Interoperability Model (DIIM)

datasets and domain-specific ontologies or standards as input and generates an annotated Knowledge Graph as output. DIIM Semantic Similarity Scoring Tool (DS3T) [14] compares the similarity between terms used in datasets and ontologies/standards. DS3T stores the found similarity results in a Semantic Similarity Score Ontology (S3O) [14] with reference links to the respective terms and their originating documents (datasets or standards/ontologies), which use these terms.

B. QoE 5G/6G Showcase and Evaluation

In the QoE 5G/6G showcase, we want to harmonize *AleksandrIvchenko* and *LIVENetflix* datasets so that they can be used in the above-mentioned case study on QoE prediction without manually integrating the datasets. At DIIM’s *transform* step, we make them syntactically interoperable by transforming them from Comma-separated Values (CSV) into RDF format with RDF Mapping Language (RML) [3], i.e. converting them into knowledge graphs. Now, these knowledge graphs can be converted into an application-specific format by a RDF-converter if an application doesn’t support CSV format. For DIIM’s *align & store* step, we set up with the DS3T, which takes two inputs, datasets (*AleksandrIvchenko* [12], *DashReStreamer* [6], and *LIVENetflix* [2]) and standards (*QoEAnalysis* [7] and *IEEEIQA* [17]), and generates a S3O with facts on similarity between terms used in given inputs. DS3T calcu-

Count of Term by Document and Extraction Type

Fig. 3. Count of distinct terms extracted manually and by DS3T from input datasets and standards

lates the similarity between two unigram terms by applying String-search Matching (SSM) algorithm implemented by *difflib* [5] and stores the results in S3O. To examine the similarity calculation results, we can load the S3O in an ontology editor, e.g., Protege [10], and query it with SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language (SPARQL). DS3T can also export similarity results in CSV format, which can be imported into a more user-friendly tool, like *Excel* or *PowerBI* [9]. Figure 3 compares the number of extracted distinct terms from the inputs. Since manually extracting distinct terms from domain-specific standards and datasets can become challenging for humans, but DS3T proves more feasible.

Figure 4 shows SSM-based similar terms found in datasets and standards for *seqpsnr* used in *AleksandrIvchenko* dataset. Figure 5 shows SSM-based similar terms found in datasets and standards for *stalling* used in the *AleksandrIvchenko* dataset. We annotate the terms *seqpsnr* and *stalling* in the *AleksandrIvchenko* graph with links to similar terms in the *LIVENetflix* graph and also annotate the *LIVENetflix* graph towards *AleksandrIvchenko* graph. With a federated SPARQL query using both terms *seqpsnr* from *AleksandrIvchenko* and

Document of Term	Term	Similarity Value	Similar Term	Document of Similar Term
AleksandrIvchenko	seqpsnr	0.73	psnr	DashReStreamer
AleksandrIvchenko	seqpsnr	0.73	psnr	IEEEIQA
AleksandrIvchenko	seqpsnr	0.73	psnr	LIVENetflix
AleksandrIvchenko	seqpsnr	0.73	psnr	QoEAnalysis
AleksandrIvchenko	seqpsnr	0.57	psnrhvs	LIVENetflix
AleksandrIvchenko	seqpsnr	0.57	psnrseqi	LIVENetflix
AleksandrIvchenko	seqpsnr	0.57	psnrvec	LIVENetflix
AleksandrIvchenko	seqpsnr	0.53	psnrhyst	LIVENetflix
AleksandrIvchenko	seqpsnr	0.53	psnrmean	LIVENetflix
AleksandrIvchenko	seqpsnr	0.53	psnrperc	LIVENetflix

Fig. 4. SSM-based similar terms found by DS3T for term *seqpsnr* in datasets and domain-specific standards

Document of Term	Term	Similarity Value	Similar Term	Document of Similar Term
AleksandrIvchenko	stalling	0.77	stall	DashReStreamer
AleksandrIvchenko	stalling	0.77	stall	QoEAnalysis
AleksandrIvchenko	stalling	0.63	stalldur	DashReStreamer
AleksandrIvchenko	stalling	0.63	stalldur	QoEAnalysis

Fig. 5. SSM-based similar terms found by DS3T for term *stalling* in datasets and domain-specific standards

psnr *LIVENetflix*, we can extract data from these graphs as a single source. Therefore, they have become harmonized and a single integrated linked data source. Similarly, we annotate *AleksandrIvchenko* and *LIVENetflix* with links to other datasets and domain-specific standards, e.g., *DashReStreamer*, *IEEEIQA*, and *QoEAnalysis*, to enhance their interoperability in the QoE domain.

V. CONCLUSION

We introduced the harmonizing issues that arise when predicting 5G/6G data sourced from different applications, which don't necessarily use the same representation format or label terms differently to label the same data values in their data models. To address these issues, we proposed the DIIM approach and showcased DIIM's application and evaluation of datasets and standards from the QoE domain. We found similar terms in datasets and standards using the SSM algorithm in DS3T. By storing the 5G/6G data in separate knowledge graphs and interlinking their terms based on similarity, we can query the data from any graph and regard it as single-sourced data. In the case study, we have presented the benefit of QoE prediction across datasets, although they don't originate from the same application. In future, we will investigate other NLP algorithms for term alignment.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported by the European Union through the Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Research and Innovation Staff Exchange Programme "Research Collaboration and Mobility for Beyond 5G Future Wireless Networks (RECOMBINE)" under Grant no. 872857. This work is financed by the European UnionNextGenerationEU through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, BG-RRP-2.005 -"Twinning" with Project No. BG-RRP-2.005-002 titled "Twinning for Excellence in Research in Sustainable Future Communication Networks in the Context of a Green Economy – GREENBEAT".

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